

THE ROLE OF VOCABULARY KNOWLEDGE IN LISTENING COMPREHENSION

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Annotation. This article aims to help learners to gain a wide range of vocabulary knowledge is a fundamental issue for improving their general language proficiency globally, and no less so in classes teaching English as a foreign language (EFL) in China (Silver, Hu, & Iino, 2002). Discussion often focuses on the comparative merits of intentional learning and of incidental learning, where learners unintentionally “pick up” vocabulary knowledge when they are focused on understanding the meaning of the language input (Hulstijn, 2001). Whereas vocabulary gains tend to be smaller for the latter (Laufer & Girsai, 2008), perhaps because learners’ attention is on global meaning rather than on individual vocabulary items, pedagogical activities can be used alongside a focus on meaning to enhance the salience of items (Sharwood Smith, 1991) and hence noticing (Schmidt, 1990) and thence vocabulary learning (Laufer, 2005). Listening proficiency, and instructional conditions, factors useful to bear in mind when planning activities to enhance vocabulary learning through listening.

Keywords: Vocabulary learning; proficiency; listening; instruction; Sharwood Smith, 1991) and hence noticing (Schmidt, 1990) and thence vocabulary learning (Laufer, 2005).

Introduction: The extent to which vocabulary knowledge can be acquired through listening has received less research attention than is the case for reading. A common thread running through the literature, however, is, first, that levels of vocabulary learning from listening are typically much lower than for reading (Brown, Waring, & Donkaewbua, 2008; Vidal, 2011); and, second, that listening may develop what van Zeeland and Schmitt (2013a) call the earlier-acquired aspects of vocabulary knowledge, such as form recognition, rather than “high levels of knowledge” (p. 609), such as meaning recognition and recall. Amounts of learning through listening may also depend on learners’ level of proficiency, in the form of either general proficiency, prior vocabulary knowledge, or specifically listening proficiency. For example, Vidal (2011), in a study comparing incidental vocabulary learning by university-level L2 learners through both reading and listening, found that for pretest to posttest gains, the higher learners’ general proficiency level was, the smaller was the difference between gains made from reading and gains made from listening. Lower proficiency learners, especially at the very lowest levels of proficiency, retained very few words from the spoken input (fewer than from reading), possibly, according to Vidal, because they were hampered by difficulties in segmenting words from the speech stream, rendering attention to vocabulary problematic.

Background Literature:

These somewhat contradictory findings may result from the more complex relationship between vocabulary knowledge and listening comprehension compared with vocabulary knowledge and reading, with implications for how important vocabulary knowledge is for vocabulary learning through listening. First, a wide range of correlations between vocabulary knowledge and listening has

been found in previous research, varying between $r = 0.209$ to $r = 0.941$ in an unpublished meta-analysis of 26 studies between 2000 and 2018 (Smith, 2019). This range may reflect differences across studies in how vocabulary knowledge has been measured. Commentators such as Stæhr (2009) argue that aural vocabulary tests should be used rather than written tests in explorations of the relationship, a view supported empirically by Cheng and Matthews (2018)

On Listening Comprehension:

Aural comprehension establishes a base for the development of oral language within the speech chain of listening and speaking (Denes & Pinson, 1993, as cited in Morley, 2001). Morley (2001) stresses the importance of listening comprehension with the claim that “listening comprehension lessons are a vehicle for teaching elements of grammatical structure and allow new vocabulary items to be contextualized within a body of communicative discourse” (p. 70). Listening comprehension is also seen as the primary channel for language input and acquisition (Peterson, 2001) providing the learners with both linguistic and non-linguistic sources. Thus, helping them construct meaning through these sources to identify the phonological, lexical, syntactic, semantic and pragmatic knowledge as well as the knowledge of the content, topic or general knowledge of the world (Rost, 2002). On the other hand, as Rost (2002) states, word segmentation and recognition form the basis of spoken language comprehension which implies that if the learners are not able to recognize a certain number of words in the input, they will fail to construct meaningful representations of any text. As a result, they might be deprived of any access to relevant contextual information. However, as Stæhr (2009) states, “knowledge of a word is no guarantee that the word will actually be recognized in continuous speech. Moreover, recognizing most of the words in the input, does not guarantee comprehension, as many other factors also affect L2 comprehension” (p. 581). These additional factors are first language listening ability (Vandergrift, 2006), text type (Shohamy & Inbar, 1991), background knowledge and topic familiarity (Schmidt-Rinehardt, 1994) and purpose of listening. Therefore, it is important to note the following points; research on listening comprehension shows that any listening comprehension test should cover a wide range of topics and text types; the background knowledge of the learners is to be considered while preparing a listening text and, thereby, the listening construct needs to be defined.

Methods:

Step 1: Vocabulary

In Step 1, educators select vocabulary to teach. Hadley and Burke (2021) suggest that educators teach words that may be difficult for children to learn from exposure alone; are conceptually related; are moderate in difficulty, useful, and related to a theme; and are selected with individual learner characteristics in mind. Often, an early childhood curriculum will specify a set of vocabulary specific to the theme that includes words most preschoolers are unlikely to know; these are often called tier 2 words within one commonly used framework for selecting vocabulary (Beck et al., 2002).

Step 2: Identify Classroom Activities

In Step 2, educators identify classroom activities for teaching vocabulary. Everyday experiences in early childhood classrooms include: (a) planned, (b) child-directed, and (c) routine activities (Johnson et al., 2015). Planned activities, such as an art project or small group early literacy lesson, have specific steps and would not occur without adult planning and facilitation.

Step 3: Identify Teaching Strategies

In Step 3, educators identify strategies for teaching target vocabulary across activities (see Table 2). Once educators select target vocabulary and identify activities, they can intentionally teach those vocabulary across activities through a variety of strategies including modeling (verbally stating the target vocabulary while pairing the statement with an object or action) and expansions (adding a word or words to what a child says) (Vanderbilt KidTalk. [n.d.]). When focusing on nouns and adjectives, this might include placing specific materials within centers during choice time. When focusing on verbs and adverbs, educators might engage in specific actions or activities to model the verb.

Step 4: Deliver Instruction and Collect Data

In Step 4, educators deliver instruction and collect data. As educators deliver vocabulary instruction for all children in their classroom, they should use strategies to create a language rich environment and to teach specific target vocabulary words (see Fig. 2). In addition, educators should monitor all children's progress toward learning target vocabulary by collecting data.

CONCLUSION: The acquisition of vocabulary is arguably the most critical component of successful language Learning. Until recently, however, it has been difficult to determine the most important Phrases and words needed to establish a suitable vocabulary for conducting conversation most effectively. The task at hand, therefore, is to talk this new information and apply it in The classroom. Since there are so many things to learn about to teach piece of Vocabulary (meaning, spoken/written forms, collocations, connotations, grammar etc.) it is Important that we as teachers only introduce a little at a time, starting with the most frequent, Useful, and less frequent uses of o'previously learned items. This paper tries to give them some Techniques and methods to build ESL learner"s knowledge of vocabulary. Based on the results of the pre-questionnaire and the vocabulary pre-test it can be seen That students encounter many difficulties in learning vocabulary. Besides, although English News is available on a lot of social media, many students rarely listen to English News to learn vocabulary.

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